

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OYEDOTUN****FIRST NAME: TEMITAYO DEBORAH****PROGRAM CODE: DIDOL****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author uses Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID).

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. With reference to the rules for writing academic essays, identify from the options the best flow diagram that outlines the basic process required for writing an essay.
 - Create topic ---- Research the topic ---- Organise points ---- Draft & Review.¹**
 - Research the topic ---- Create topic ---- Organise points & Review --- Draft.
 - Create topic ---- Organise points ---- Research the topic ---- Draft & Review.
 - Organise points & Review ---- Research the topic ---- Create topic ---- Draft.
2. A Paragraph is effectively developed with all the options below *except*
 - the presentation of a controlling idea with related supporting details.
 - an adequate discussion of the main idea with appropriate rhetorical strategies.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 8.

- a coherent analysis and interpretation of arguments and secondary claims.
- the evidence of a thesis sentence, empirical facts and opinions.**²

3. From the options below, select the correct statement in relation to essay writing conventions.

- Essays are nonfictional write-ups with structured development of debates and reports.
- Essay is an academic writing structured formally to present an organised discussion of evidence-based arguments.**³
- Essays comprise paragraphs with annotated facts and subjective arguments.
- Essays are similar to other academic write-ups and technical reports.

4. Secondary claims and supports are crucial to research arguments and empirical findings. These sources and claims, however, need to be assessed for validity, reliability and relevance before they are cited and referenced in academic research. From the options below, select the most important factor that can be considered in order to assess the reliability of a journal publication.

- The article is published, frequently assessed and available online.
- The journal is recent and has current topics and a site map or link.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 11.

³ Ibid., 7.

- The article is published by a reputable organisation and scholar and is peer-reviewed.⁴**
- The journal is popular, provides standard abstracts and is published with DOI and index number.
5. From the following options, select one appropriate technique to avoid plagiarism while engaging with sources within a text.
- abbreviate quotations and provide citations with the full bibliographic notes.
- provide the summary of the relevant note from the author, with citations, page numbers and references.⁵**
- paraphrase a few words from the original text, cite the page and reference accordingly.
- supply verbatim quotes of related claims with/without in-text citations and references.
6. Annotated Bibliographies are mostly signalled by....
- a brief description of works enclosed in brackets after the publication data.⁶**
- a header explaining the principles and the importance of the items in the reference list.
- the footnote outlining the description of the publication data.
- the list of full entries of publications, arranged alphabetically on the reference page.

⁴ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 42.

⁵ *Ibid.*, 50 – 51.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 155.

7. Grant, Susan., & Krest, Leone. "The Girl Woman. " Lam Randle, May 5, 2010

In Turabian/Chicago style, the above bibliography indicates a way of referencing a

book or Chapters in Books.

Journal.

Newspaper.

magazine.⁷

8. From the options below, select the correct form that best represents the Chicago referencing style for books and chapters in a book.

Oyedotun, T. D. T. (2020). "Guide Rock". Guyana: Landmark Voice.

Oyedotun, Temitope D., T. 2020. "Guide rock". Guyana: Landmark Voice.

Oyedotun, Temitope D. Timothy, 2020. *Guide Rock*. Guyana: Landmark Voice.⁸

Oyedotun, Temitope. D. T. *Guide Rock*. Guyana: Landmark Voice (2020).

9. The research paradigm, which is based on the theory that knowledge emanates from observation and logical inference, is known as

Postpositivism.⁹

Pragmatism.

Social Constructivism.

⁷ Kate Turabian, 194.

⁸ Ibid., 244.

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Volpe Marie, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Fourth ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 147.

Critical Theory.

10. With reference to the research process and methods, identify the incorrect statement from the option below.

- Research is an intellectual inquiry undertaken to provide solutions to problems.
- Research reliability is a method which outlines a clear discussion of the empirical findings.¹⁰**
- Triangulation is critical to understanding phenomena in research.
- Research is a systemic formation of hypothesis, data analysis and critical interpretation of data.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Fourth ed. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Gulma Kabiru. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

¹⁰ Ibid., 160.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.